

The Speech Events

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ABSTRACT

The use of linguistics has become an important part of the teaching and learning process in and out of the class. It gives knowledge of the rules which controls of language as a system of communication. The speech events are interesting because the contextual factors relation involves. Knowing only grammar is not enough. So language must be appropriate to the situation and participants. By studying sociolinguistics, we can interact politely studying and appropriately in social situations.

KEYWORDS: linguistics, teaching, learning, communication, sociolinguistics

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I. INTRODUCTION

Linguistic is the study of language as a system of human communication. When a language is studied, it is also necessary to know the varieties of a language used by different social classes in different social situations. In this way, linguistics overlaps with sociology and a new field of study called social linguistics.

To know language as a formal system we need to know not only the rules which generate well – formed sentences but also language as a means of social interaction. We need to know those conventions of use which control the selection of well formed sentences appropriate to a particular social situation.

Therefore “Learning a language” means learning the rules of use as well as the rules of the formal linguistic system.

In Sociolinguistics, speech events are interesting because the contextual factors relate each other and some have an influence upon the other. By studying the constituent factors of a speech event, we can use language appropriately to a social context.

II. THE SPEECH EVENT

The speech event may be defined as a piece of linguistic interaction, a communicate happening consisting of one or more utterances.

For example, the kind of exchange which takes place between a traveler and a ticket collector is a speech event, as are lengthier exchanges such as that between a door – to – door salesman and his prospective customer and that between two houses – wives gossiping over the garden wall. The speech event will be studied with its constituent factors.

The most obvious constituents of a speech event are as follows.

- A. Addresser and Addressee
- B. Message Form
- C. Channel
- D. Setting
- E. Topic
- F. Code

A. Addresser and Addressee

To start from an analysis of a speech event, there must be at least two participants, the “I” and “You” or “a speaker” and “a hearer” or “the addresser and the addressee.” The addresser is the one who sends a message and the addressee is the one who receives the message. Both addresser and addressee may be singular or –plural. So the speech event may take place.

- 1. One to One
- 2. One to Many
- 3. Many to One
- 4. Many to Many

As the addresser need not be physically, present or may not be known as an individual. We don't know in speaking and writing by identifying them as members of a group.

B. Message Form

A “Message” is something that the addresser sends to the Addressee. What is conveyed in speech or writing from one person to one or more other people. The message may not always be stated in verbal form but be conveyed by other means.

For example.....a wink, gestures. Although the message is usually verbal it may be transmitted without verbal means at all.

For example ... signs and signals “spoken” and “written” forms are verbal message while “Gesture” and “Graphic” are nonverbal.

According to the situation, the same message can be communicated in variety of different ways. If it is extensive, we may have to shorten; if formal, we will select a different set of words.

C. Channel

Another constituent factor in speech event is “channel” through which a message is conveyed. For communication to take place, contact must be established between the Addresser and Addressee. Just the physical nearness of two people does not establish a speech situation. So to get the attention of people, a channel of communication must be opened and also maintained with our perceiving senses such as –

- Hearing (Auditory)**
- Sight (visual)**
- Hearing+ sight (Audio-Visual)**
- Touching (Tactile)**

Auditory Channel is represented by sound waves passing through the air and perceived our sense of hearing.

Visual Channel is stated by marks at the sense of sight.

Therefore writing is regarded as “Language in the visual medium” and speaking as “language aural medium.” Gestures also make appeal to the visual. Since, thus writing and gesture are different media which make use of the same channel.

But writing is not always apprehended by the sense of sight. So Tactile is a channel which makes appeal to the sense of touch.

Audio-Visual Channel makes use of both senses of hearing and sight. One may use both the aural and the visual channel of gesture Therefore, in many speech events. One may use more than one channel at the same time.

D. Setting

The time and place of a speech event is called the setting. For example- a conversation can take place in a classroom, a garden, a church, and it can take place at any hour of the day. The setting of a speech event may have an effect on what it is said.

Conversation or communication between people does not take place in a vacuum but at a particular time and place, in a physical and temporal setting, they may be in a crowd or alone, among friends or strangers, in a street or court. All these factors may play a part in what goes on in the conversation.

E. Topic

Topic is what is talked about or written about. Indifferent speech communities, there are different rules about what topics may or may not be discussed. For example, in some communities, illness, death, a person’s age may be considered unsuitable topics for conversation. There is always about something a prepositional element or topic in

an utterance. So topic is an important element in the speech situation.

F. Code

Any system of signals can be used for sending a message. A natural language is an example of a code, as are more code Braille and sign language. We may not be able to communicate, with another person if we do not share the same seed of code for verbal conversations or if we have no linguistic code in common. The paralinguistic code is, to some degree at least, known both addresser and addressee. Although the factors are separated, they interrelate in complex ways in particular speech events. The setting may have a very definite effect on the channel not channel not because of physical circumstances in which an exchange takes place; thus bookmakers at racecourses convey information about betting odds by the use of signs not only to preserve secrecy but to overcome the noise of the crowd, which would drown out any attempts at speech.

The setting also determines the message form. Most Myanmar religious ceremonies are opened by reciting “နမောတဿ (namawtatha). ဘဂဝတေ (bagawatow) ၊ အရဟတေ (arahatow) ၊ သမုတသဗ္ဗုဒ္ဓဓဿ (thamarthemavoadatha)” there times. The setting is religious and the message form of reciting “နမောတဿ” is appropriate ate to the setting.

The setting code and topic are often interrelated. For example –There are certain topics of conversation which are not suitable during mealtimes. Sometimes, setting relates to code in bilingual Situations For example, In the Middle Ages, theological matters were discussed in Latin though they used their own languages in other communication.

Topic is related to the addresser and addressee.

For example:

Men and women have different things to talk about Therefore men hardly talk about babies feeding times. Each of the factor the addresser, the addressee, the channel, the linguistic code used the setting, the topic and the form of the message, plays an essential role in everyday speech situation. We are able to understand what variety to use in what situation, how to vary the style according to whom we are addressing when to speak or remain silent.

III. CONCLUSION

To sum up, knowing only grammar is not enough Language must be appropriate to the situation and participants. By studying sociolinguistics we can interact politely studying and appropriately in social situations. That is why; I like courteously sociolinguistics very much.

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